

Creative

reading

~~exercises~~

hacks!

c*o*n*t*e*n*t*s

1. you are here ②
2. reading as a method of protest or why this zine? ③
a few words from Anastasiya
3. a few words from Alice ⑦
4. hack 1: second-hand reading ⑨
5. untitled artwork ⑪
6. poem 'practice' ⑫
7. hack 2: reading choir ⑬
8. Alice's personal experience ⑮/⑯
9. hack 3: dialogical reading ⑰
10. hack 4: why do books have two pages ⑲
11. hack 5: you are what you read ⑳
12. hack 6: reading in your body ㉓
13. hack 7: reading in repetition ㉕
14. poem 'offline' ㉖
15. thanks ㉘

i*n*t*r*o

BY THE AUTHORS.

WHO?

Reading as a method of protest or why this zine? A few words from Anastasiya

Do we ever pause to ask: why do I read the way I do? For a long time, I never did. During my studies, I was taught to skim and scan academic texts, accelerating through lines as if they were checkpoints, always knowing what I was meant to find, not letting myself to be surprised by what I read. Often, reading the abstract, introduction and conclusion of a paper was enough to add one more citation to my manuscript.

These practices seemed to me natural and almost inevitable in academia. It was only when I finally asked myself whose powers are embedded in these ways of reading — efficiency, extraction, productivity — that it struck me: reading had become a form of knowledge mining. A stripping of meaning at high speed. Consumption of words as resources. Realizing this didn't feel good, that even a practice as intimate as reading could be reshaped by the negative power of capitalism. Yet this unsettled feeling was a way to imagine reading otherwise.

From there, I began to reflect on how power is embedded in the most mundane academic practices — reading, writing, teaching, giving critique. I started organizing workshops to rethink these practices and to experiment with alternative ways of being in academia, inviting artists and humanities scholars to share their interpretations, while also giving workshops myself. These efforts have come together in a series called Doing Academia Otherwise at Tilburg Law School. This zine idea grows out of that series — a small embodiment that might carry its questions into other communities and spaces.

One of the workshops I gave on reading as a method of protest, took place at a summer school on Activism in and with Academia in Rome in July, 2025. There I met Alice, a full-time activist and illustrating artist. The moment she gave me her stickers on the first day, my admiration was instant and irreversible (if love has a language, mine would be sharing stickers). After this workshop, titled Reading as a Method of Protest, Alice came to me and shared a story about how her and her activist group had been detained after a climate protest, and how reading collectively in a cell became an act of not giving up and a continuation of the fight even behind bars. Thanks to Alice, her story, and her excitement to explore these questions together, this zine became a real thing you are holding.

This zine is a grab bag of reading exercises — or hacks (we were not sure, which word to use) — you can do in your reading groups, book clubs, with colleagues, students, friends, or complete strangers. Some exercises came from our own experiments, while others were pinched from other people's ideas and blended with our own in this messy, magical portion of collective intellect. When we know who to credit, we do — because credit is part of the fun. But this collection is not about the ownership of it. It's about letting these ideas out in the world, hoping that they spark some acts of being together, thinking together, and reading differently. That said, we encourage you to take anything you like, reprint it, remix it, share it, and let it mutate however it wants.

Reading as a way of escaping confinement. A few words from Alice

Reading for me is a form of escape and a way to tend to my soul, to make it rest or allow it to travel far away and then come back to me. Books keep me company. I am a lover of novels, and I also love reading out loud, or listening to people do it. This is something I grew fond of as an adult, as I never really had that “bedtime story” be such a huge deal in my family. When covid hit, I was isolated with a group of friends in a big house by the lake. We spent our days making up stories and reading each other books, always inventing new ways of making them compelling for our few but keen listeners. Our words lulled us to sleep, tickled our spirits, drew tears from our eyes. It was intense, and beautiful.

Some of the exercises you find here come from that experience. Now that they are making their way into the world, I shall imagine being a small fly, perched on walls listening to other groups of friends, all cozied up with blankets, sitting on top of each other in tiny squishy sofas, reading in the most bizarre ways. I hope you savour those moments to the last drop :)

Another moment when reading became crucial for me, was when I joined a movement of civil disobedience, where my comrades and I would engage in direct actions and then get arrested. I cannot count how many hours we ended up spending confined in the tiny cells or the nondescript, beige corridors one can find in pretty much any Italian police station. Books played a huge role in that period of my life, because what we read were oftentimes the words of those who came before us. Nelson Mandela, Angela Davis, Martin Luther King, or the partigiani, who fought against fascism. They were our inspiration and reading them together made our time spent in those cells even more meaningful. Those tiny black letters, printed who knows how

many years ago, were like threads, tiny strings which could run through time and connect us to them, whom we liked to believe were the “us” of the past. What did they think while they served their time in prison or being oppressed? How did they endure so many hardships and still managed to keep up their moral values and ethos? What gave them the strength to keep fighting? We were hungry for answers, maybe even a bit morbidly curious, and in desperate need to believe that what we were doing had even a slight chance of succeeding in making the world a better place. Did we manage to follow in their footsteps? Yes and no. But we still have chapters to write for the next generation of rebels.

You can see why, as soon as Anastasiya and I began talking about this Zine, I was more than eager to jump in! She’s such an attentive listener and intelligent, creative, curious person, and a woman I instantly felt at home with. It has been a huge pleasure working with her to bring this collection of reading hacks to life!

second-hand

reading

HACK 1

OH YES I DO!
I WAS FASCINATED.
IT SEEMED LIKE I
WAS IN ON SOMEBODY
ELSE'S SECRETS, OR INSIDE
THEIR MINDS.

Remember that book you borrowed from the library, where someone else had scribbled notes and underlined things in the margins? You spent so long trying to decipher those squiggles.

FUNNY,
WORRYING
LINES

It was so absorbing, as if a mysterious stranger from the past left a whisper for you, humming between the lines.

Second-hand reading, writing, or drawing is a practice of dancing in the margins. I like this technique because reading alongside another reader can inspire you to respond or begin writing or drawing yourself. It feels less lonely like you have a companion to respond to.

WTF!

How to try it? Start a book-crossing adventure with friends or colleagues. Each of you reads one book, leaves your scribbles and diagrams, and then passes the book onto each other. If multiple people add notes, use different coloured pens to layer your voices. By the end, you'll have a quiet conversation unfolding, folding, and refolding across the pages.

SO NICE TO DO IT
WITH PEOPLE YOU LOVE/TRUST!

I ALSO SOMETIMES FIND
THAT NOWADAYS, SERIES ARE
TRENDING AND WE TEND TO
TALK ABOUT THOSE A LOT.

WHAT IF WE COULD
HAVE THOSE CONVERSATIONS
ABOUT BOOKS... AND/OR ON
THE BOOKS THEMSELVES?!

Watch an artwork by William Kentridge (2017)
'Second-Hand Reading'

I learnt about second-hand reading at the Deleuze&Guattari Camp 2025, thanks to Anette Göthlund and Annika Hellman, who were inspired by the library of Ulla Lind (1951-2023).

PRACTICE

WRITING, WRITING, WRITING
IT IS NOT JUST A GAME

WANTING TO BE READ
BUT ALSO WANTING TO BE HEARD

HOW TO FEEL FREE ON PAPER
WHEN EVEN WORD IS NOW COMPLETING MY SENTENCES

HOW TO THINK AND WRITE WHAT I FOUND
WITHOUT WORRYING ABOUT BEING PUBLISHED

WITHOUT RACING TOWARDS THE END
BUT HAVE TIME TO BE WELL SPENT

- ALMA BEŠIĆ -

Artwork: Untitled by Anaëlle Bueno Patin

reading choir

HACK 2

Reading Choir is a collective exercise to practice how reading is not only about what you read but about how and with whom you read. It can open up the whole palette of textures and colors: fusion of voices and their vibrations, harmony in the music of different language, the intonations, the speed, the volume, the noise, the childhood memories of someone reading aloud to you, the power of collective presence, and... and... and...

13

How can you use this technique? Assign one person as the conductor, and everyone else is the choir. All except the conductor brings a text - poem, prose, terms and conditions, whatever you want (it doesn't have to be in a shared language, the more languages, the better). You all seat in a circle or in a choir-like structure, on the floor or on a chair, considering everyone's physical limitations. The choir begins reading aloud, all at once. After a few minutes, the conductor calls a name and the choir silences, while the called person continues reading (2-3-4 people can be called at the same time). Repeat for several rounds. Be the choir for 20-30 minutes. After that, discuss what you've noticed or how you felt, and how it changed the way you think about reading.

14

This hack was inspired by the text of Gemma Medina Estupiñán and Alessandra Saviotti in 'We Contain Multitudes; Expanding Spaces and Forms of Mentorship within Art Education and Practices', Arnhem: ArtEZ Press, 2023.

FOREWORD:

IT'S HARD FOR ME TO DRAW ANYTHING ACTIVISM-RELATED.

WHY? GREAT QUESTION.

DOCUMENTO.

CE L'HA IL SUO COLLEGA.

DOVE SEI NATA?

GLIEL'HO GIA' DETTO 20 VOLTE.

DOVE ALLOGGI?

SI EDITI.

NO.

PREFERISCO NON DIRGUELO.

TI ACCOMPAGNO IO, E TIENI LA PORTA APERTA.

COS'E' QUESTO?

E' UN LIBRO. (THIS IS AN UPRISING)

LO LASCI QUI, QUESTO LO TENIAMO NOI.

READING CREATES A TINY SPACE WHERE ONE CAN FEEL FREE

*SOMEHOW, THE FLOORS OF THE POLICE STATIONS JUST STAY COLD, NO MATTER HOW LONG YOU SIT ON THEM.

SOMETIMES WE WOULD READ OUT LOUD FOR EACH OTHER, OTHERS WE WOULD JUST SHARE MOMENTS OF SILENT READING. IT WAS NICE TO BE ABLE TO READ SOMETHING TOGETHER, AND TO EXCHANGE BOOKS. TIME PASSES

laudato si
POPE FRANCIS

SLOWLY WHEN YOU ARE IN POLICE CUSTODY,

the nutmeg's curse
AMITAV GHOSH

IT SEEMS TO NEVER GO BY. READING WAS CRUCIAL TO FILL SOME OF THOSE HOURS. IT ALSO

HELPED US FURTHER AND DEEPEN OUR KNOWLEDGE ON THE ISSUES WE WERE PASSIONATE ABOUT & PROTESTING FOR, HOWEVER SOME

women, race and class
ANGELA DAVIS

SOMETIMES I ADMIT IT WAS EXTREMELY HARD TO CONCENTRATE.

WE WERE READING WHAT WE NEEDED TO HEAR

RESISTANCE. WORDS ABOUT FREEDOM, DIGNITY, WORDS FROM THE ONES WHO CAME BEFORE US.

dialogical reading

HACK 3

To try this, choose two readings: one is your main text, something you want or need to understand; the second can be entirely unrelated but might offer a new perspective. Read a chapter/page/paragraph of the main text and reflect on its key ideas/questions. Then, open the second text at any spot and read a paragraph or a page as a response to that idea or question. It is about contrasting the main text with the other and defamiliarizing yourself. It offers a different register to experience the indeterminacy of your questions.

REALISTICALLY, I THINK THIS COMES FROM MY OWN VERY DIFFICULT EXPERIENCE OF TRYING TO THINK ABOUT SOMETHING IN THE ABSTRACT. ABSTRACT THINKING TO ME IS PIZARRE AND DOESN'T REALLY MAKE SENSE. SO, I'VE ALWAYS NEEDED TO HAVE SOMETHING TO THINK WITH OR AGAINST, OR SOME KIND OF FOIL. AND WHENEVER I, YOU KNOW, THINK ABOUT A TEXT IN THE CLASSROOM... OBVIOUSLY I'M THINKING ABOUT A READING, BUT YOU KNOW LIFE CAN ALSO BE SIMILAR. I FEEL LIKE WHEN WE TALK TO SOMEONE ABOUT AN ISSUE WE'RE HAVING IN OUR FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS OR A QUESTION ABOUT WHAT TO DO IN A JOB SITUATION OR WHATEVER

I ALSO FEEL LIKE IN THOSE SITUATIONS WE ARE KIND OF POSING TWO TEXTS AGAINST EACH OTHER. AND FROM THERE, I GUESS YOU GET AN EXPERIENCE OF A DIFFERENT PERSON'S IDEAS AND HOW THEY APPROACH SOMETHING, BUT ALSO YOU START TO APPRECIATE HOW DIFFERENTLY YOU APPROACH THINGS, AND INDEED THEN, THAT CAN HELP YOU UNDERSTAND THE DIFFERENT WAYS OF ENGAGING WITH THE WORLD.

you are what you read

#ACK 4

19

20

This way of reading is the simplest yet the most fun I have had while reading out loud. It is simple: try to engage with the audience as much as possible, by modulating your tone and voice. don't be afraid to shout or whisper, look the listeners into the eyes, pause to create suspense... and then invent your own characters. What do they sound like? what's their personality and how would they pronounce the words in the book? can you also move around and do a little impersonation? amazing. do you happen to have socks on your feet? use them to make little puppets for your hands.

The only rule here is: BRING IT. Bring everything you have to the table, win your fear, your shyness, fight with every judgemental voice in your head and.. action!

why do books have

HACKS

two pages

21

22

Not entirely sure. but what if those two pages were one, and the sentences were connected? how would they make sense, if at all?

Try to read the book you are holding by line and not by page. maybe, just maybe, another story will unfold..

r*e*a*d*i*n*g

HACK 6

When you're reading, read the sentences, making space for a physical translation of the sentence in your body. What part of your body is reading this sentence? Read it out loud from there. Don't think, just go with the first movement that comes to you through your body.
Side note: sometimes it hurts.

As you stay with it - reading from the body - pay attention to the environment and feel free to include some of the movements. How do we incorporate readings from our environment into our own reading? How does the body react to its environment? What generates a movement? How does this movement transform our way of being in that particular place and time? Observe to what extent you feel displaced, disoriented, transformed, and what that means for your reading of the space.

i*n

y*o*u*r

b*o*d*y

reading in repetition

HACK 7

When reading, try to stay with one sentence, read it over and over again, internally and aloud, try to notice the intonation you're reading with.

Do you put emphasis on particular words?
Read it over and over until you are able to release the tension and let it go.

Exercises 6 and 7 were composed by Laura Dubourjal and Marie Beauchamps for the workshop on creative reading at Tilburg University.

25

OFFLINE

LET ME BE
IN MY MEADOW OF THOUGHTS
VAST, OPEN, FREE
LET ALL IDEAS COME TO ME

LET ME UNLEARN
THAT I SHOULDN'T BE HERE
THAT I SHOULD CHASE
LOSING MY OWN PACE

LET ME IGNORE
ALL REQUESTS
AND ALL OPEN TABS
EVER-PRESENT ON MY DESK

ITS SCREAMING ATTENTION,
INTERRUPTING ME
TUGGING AT ME
WITH ITS HOT AND DRY METALLIC SCENT

LET ME OPEN INSTEAD
THE DOORS IN MY THOUGHTS
SO THE FOG-KISSED WIND
TURNS INTO A DRAFT WITH CLEAN, COLD AIR

- ALMA BEŠIĆ -

26

Huge thanks to Tilburg Law School for helping us out financially, so we could cover the printing costs and make sure Alice gets some well-deserved love — and pay — for her illustrations and creative concept work. Warm hugs and thanks to Anna Berti Suman, who led the summer school on activism and academia, for introducing us to each other — without Anna, this zine simply wouldn't be.

A big shout-out to Sarouche Razi, Siddharth De Souza, and Carlos Delclos for teaming up with us at the summer school and bringing your warm energy into these ideas. Thanks also to our collaborators Alma Bešić, Anaëlle Bueno Patin, and Richard Clements for lending your incredible creativity to this zine. To all of you, heartfelt gratitude for being the kind of generous, imaginative humans that make this academic community such a joy to be part of.

1

This zine, like anything in life, is an unfinished project. If you have your own reading hacks and don't mind sharing, please, hit us up on Instagram!

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